

Integrated Network Design and Demand Estimation for Advanced Air Mobility Using an Extended Multiple-Allocation p-Hub Median Framework

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Abstract—It is essential to take the emerging transportation mode, Advanced Air Mobility (AAM), into transportation planning for developing a safe and efficient integrated multimodal transportation system. However, there are many operational uncertainties of AAM due to technological advancements, industry development, and regulatory establishment. Instead of operational details, e.g., fleet planning, eVTOL scheduling, and passenger assignment, transportation planners and policymakers want to know potential vertiport locations and the number and spatial distribution of travelers shifting from driving to using AAM services. To address these needs, our study examines the AAM integrated network design and demand estimation from a planning perspective. Given a traffic analysis zone (TAZ)-level origin and destination (OD) demand matrix, we propose an Extended Multiple Allocation p-Hub Median Problem (E-MApHMP) to determine optimal vertiport locations and estimate the shifted demand simultaneously. The objective of the mathematical programming is to minimize system-wide generalized travel cost, or, equivalently, to maximize the savings in generalized travel cost from shifting ground demand to air. A case study of Tampa Bay Region Plus (TBR+) involves 1,526 TAZs across seven counties, assuming each TAZ could potentially host one vertiport. Given the complexity of the problem, we developed a three-part chromosome-structured Genetic Algorithm (GA) with local search strategies to solve it efficiently. The traveler and socioeconomic data for this paper were drawn from a travel demand model developed for western Florida, US. Across multiple problem instances with fixed initial seeds, the proposed genetic algorithm (GA) consistently outperformed other metaheuristic algorithms and the Gurobi solver in terms of solution quality and computational efficiency. A factorial design sensitivity analysis was conducted to identify key parameters influencing AAM demand, the share of low-income travelers, and access and egress travel distances to vertiports. Results from the Type II ANOVA indicate that vertiport processing time, vertiport parking price, and the per-mile flying fee are the most significant factors affecting these outcomes.

Keywords: Urban Air Mobility (UAM), OpenSky, Travel Demand Modeling, Three-part Chromosome Genetic Algorithm, Factorial Design Sensitivity Analysis.